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ABSTRACT

Green technology is increasingly important, especially for synthesizing gold nanoparticles (AuNPs), which are valued for their optical properties, stability, cost-effectiveness, and environmental friendliness. This study aimed to synthesize AuNPs using onion extract, rich in bioactive compounds like flavonoids and enzymes, which act as natural reducing agents. The successful synthesis of AuNPs was indicated by a color change from green to dark brown and confirmed using UV-Vis spectrophotometry, FTIR, SEM, TEM, and Zeta potential analysis. The biosynthesized AuNPs exhibited significant anticancer activity against DLA cells and antimicrobial activity against pathogens such as *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

KEYWORDS: Allium Cepa L. (onion), Biological activity. Characterization, Green synthesis, Gold Nanoparticles (AuNPs).

1. INTRODUCTION

Gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) are unique as they display size and shape-dependent, optical and electronic properties. The surface of AuNPs can be readily modified with functional groups such as thiols, phosphines, and amines for conjugating ligands such as oligonucleotides, proteins, and antibodies. These properties make AuNPs favorable for innumerable applications in medicine, electronics, materials science, alternative energy generation, environmental restoration, etc [Azzazy H M, et al. (2006), Bhattacharya R, et al. (2008), Han G, et al. (2007), Han G, et al.(2007), Jain K K. (2005), Jain K K. (2005), Jain K K. (2007), Longmire M, et al. (2008), Sonvico F, et al. (2005), Sperling R A, et al. (2008)]. Available methods for nanoparticle synthesis use toxic chemicals either in the form of reducing agents to reduce various metal salts to their corresponding nanoparticles or as stabilizing agents to prevent nanoparticles from agglomeration [Esumi K, et al. (2001), Feitz A G J. and Waite D. (2004), Lin J, et al. (2001)]. Currently, nanofabrication emphasizes the principle of 'green' nanotechnology which advocates the application of environmentally sound and non-polluting methods for the synthesis of nanoparticles and their derivatives [Beveridge T J, et al. (1980), Konish Y, et al. (2004), Mukherjee P, et al. (2001), Huang J, et al. (2007), Kasthuri J, et al (2009), Shankar S S, et al. (2004), Babu, P. J., (2011)]. The AuNPs are applied successfully in catalysis, sensor, antimicrobial, anticancer, cosmetics, gene expression, disease diagnosis, diagnostics, therapy, bio-labeling, drug delivery and pathogens detection [Divakaran et al. (2019)], microscopic imaging and targeted therapies [Klekotko et al. (2019)], sensors, antimicrobial agent, immune-assays, genomics, anticancer, imaging and monitoring of biological moieties [Naimi-Shamel et al. (2019), Nasrollahzadeh and Sajadi, (2016a)]. Regarding bio-inspired synthesis, different bio-sources have been used for the fabrication of NPs, the bioactive agents act as oxidizing agents, and metal ions are converted into stable atoms at the nanoscale. The features of NPs can be varied by changing the conditions, i.e., concentrations extract and metal ions concentration, pH, temperature, and reaction time [Nasrollahzadeh and Sajadi, (2016b), Nasrollahzadeh et al.,

(2015a, 2015b)]. Because of disadvantages and undesirable influence of conventional synthesis techniques, the green route is preferred to avoid the environmental pollution and health impacts [Awwad *et al.* (2021a, 2021b), Bhavani *et al.* (2018), Elayakumar *et al.* (2019), Elsherif *et al.* (2021), Jaganathan *et al.* (2019), Khodadadi *et al.* (2017b), Manikandan *et al.* (2018), Sasmaz *et al.* (2018, 2019), Sinanoglu and Sasmaz, (2019)]. Because of the aforementioned facts and advantages of the bio-inspired synthesis of AuNPs, this review article emphasizes the green synthesis and applications of AuNPs. The bio-inspired synthesis agents include plants, algae, fungi, and biomolecules. The effect of reaction conditions on the bioinspired synthesis of AuNPs and prospects was also discussed. The onion (*Allium cepa*) is a widely cultivated plant all over the world and used plants, and its bulb (onion) is used as both food and medicine. Onions possess strong, characteristic aromas and flavors, which have made them important ingredients in various food items. Onions and onion flavors (essential oils) are important seasonings widely used in food processing. It has been shown that onion possesses various biological properties, including antibiotic, antidiabetic, antioxidant, antiatherogenic, anticancer effects, antimicrobial, antioxidant, antiparasitic, and anti-inflammatory activities [Lampe, J. W. (1999), Corea G, *et al.* (2005)]. E-waste materials present a complex environmental challenge, containing diverse pollutants including metals (Cu, Ag, Au, Pt, Cd, Cr, Al, Li, Hg, Ni), plastics, glass, printed circuit boards, and electronic components. These materials release toxic elements like arsenic, cadmium, chromium, mercury, and lead into environmental systems, posing significant risks to both ecosystem and human health Bansal, A., *et al.* (2023). Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have emerged as a promising technological solution, demonstrating superior organic pollutant removal efficiency compared to traditional activated carbon. The critical nature of e-waste management requires advanced technological interventions that can simultaneously address environmental contamination and potential resource recovery, with nanomaterial-based technologies offering innovative approaches to mitigating these complex challenges Dodamani, S., *et al.* (2021).

Figure 1: Different methods for synthesis of gold nanoparticle, (Santhosh, P. B. *et al.* (2022)).

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Parida, U. K., *et al.* (2011) synthesized environment-friendly gold nanoparticles using onion (*Allium cepa*) extract as the reducing agent. The nanoparticles were characterized using UV-visible, XRD, and SEM, TEM methods. The absorption peak at 540 nm was found to be broadened with the increase in time indicating the polydispersity nature of the nanoparticles. The XRD results suggested that the crystallization of the bio-organic phase occurs on the surface of the gold nanoparticles or vice versa. The broadening of peaks in the XRD patterns was attributed to particle size effects. The internalization of nanoparticles within cells could occur via processes including phagocytosis, fluid-phase endocytosis, and receptor-mediated endocytosis. Patra, J. K., *et al.* (2016) demonstrated the green synthesis of gold nanoparticles (OP-AuNPs) using dried onion peel extract. The OP-AuNPs, characterized by various techniques, showed strong antibacterial, anticandidal, antioxidant, and proteasome inhibitory activities, highlighting their potential applications in biomedical, cosmetic, food, and pharmaceutical industries. Menon, S., *et al.*, (2017) reviewed AuNPs are one of the widely used particles as it has many therapeutic applications, such as drug delivery systems for many diseases like cancer, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes mellitus, biosensors, and environmental applications of dye degradation, bioremediation of toxic chemicals present in the environment (soil and atmosphere). AuNPs synthesis by the green route has become the latest development, because of the bioavailability of sources like plants or microorganisms, and it also reduces the utilization of toxic chemicals. This review explains the various microorganisms like bacteria, algae, fungi, actinomycetes, and yeast involved in the synthesis of these nanoparticles and also elucidates the size, shape, and functional groups involved in the synthesis of nanoparticles and their applications. Acharya, P., *et al.* (2019)

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explored the green synthesis of AgNPs and AuNPs using onion extracts as reducing agents. Characterized by various techniques, these nanoparticles, along with turmeric and citrus oil-based nanoemulsions, were used to prime-aged onion seeds. Internalization studies confirmed the absorption of nanoparticles into seeds. Greenhouse and field trials revealed improved seed germination, emergence, growth, and yield. AuNPs treatment led to a significant increase in seed emergence (63.2%) compared to unprimed seeds (37.4%) and a 23.9% yield improvement. Phukan, K., et al. (2021) studied that utilized onion peel extract to synthesize gold nano-bioconjugates with high antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities, primarily due to quercetin. The ethyl acetate fraction showed the best results. Nano-bioconjugates demonstrated significant cell viability and ROS reduction, proving more effective than the onion peel extract alone. Tan, G., et al. (2023) investigated the antioxidative and anticancer properties of AuNPs synthesized using onion and garlic extracts. The AuNPs, sized 5-18 nm, were well-dispersed and stable. Gallic acid was a common phenolic compound in both extracts, enhancing radical scavenging activities. Garlic-derived AuNPs (GAuNPs) showed a stronger anticancer effect, while onion-derived AuNPs (OAuNPs) more effectively induced apoptosis in MCF-7 cells. Both types inhibited cell migration in healthy and cancerous cells and exhibited cytotoxicity through modulation of proliferation, apoptosis, and motility, with the onion extract showing higher radical scavenging potential.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

1. Reagents and Chemicals

Tetrachloroauric acid (HAuCl₄.XH₂O) was obtained from Sigma Aldrich. Freshly prepared double and triple distilled water was used throughout the experimental work [Parida, U. K., et al. (2011)].

2. Biological synthesis of AuNPs

Method 1. The broth used for the reduction of Au³⁺ ions to Au⁰ was prepared by taking 10 g of thoroughly washed and finely cut onions in 500 mL Erlenmeyer flasks with 40 mL of sterile distilled water and then boiling it for 15 min. In a typical experiment, 0.2 mL of broth was added to 50 mL of 10⁻³ M aqueous chloroauric acid (HAuCl₄) solution. Within an hour (50 minutes) cherry red solution was obtained [Parida, U. K., et al. (2011)].

Method 2. To prepare the onion extract, fresh onions are washed, peeled, and chopped into small pieces. These are then boiled in distilled water for about 10-15 minutes to release the bioactive compounds. The solution is filtered to remove solid matter, and the extract is stored at 4°C until use. The synthesis process involves mixing the onion extract with a 1 mM solution of HAuCl₄ in a 1:1 ratio. The mixture is stirred at room temperature or gently heated between 40-60°C for about 20-30 minutes. During this time, a color change from pale yellow to ruby red indicates the reduction of Au³⁺ ions to gold nanoparticles (Au⁰) [Rajeshkumar, S., and Bharath, L. V. (2017), Mansoori, G. A., and Soelaiman, T. (2005)].

Figure 2: Green synthesis of AuNPs from a plant. Plant extract and metal salt solution HAuCl₄ were mixed. After that, the resultant solution is centrifuged, which results in the bio-reduction of metallic ions to AuNPs. Phytochemicals act as reducing, as well as stabilizing/ capping, agents in this process. The resultant AuNPs are characterized by using SEM, TEM, FTIR, XRD, etc. (Bharadwaj, K. K., et al. (2021))

4. BIOSYNTHETIC MECHANISMS OF AuNPS

The mechanism of AuNPs biosynthesis is a simple two-step process and does not require a dramatic increase in temperature and pressure. In the first step, the biological extract (e.g., plant, bacterial, or fungal extract) is mixed with the HAuCl₄ salt solution, which causes the reduction of gold (Au³⁺) ions to gold atoms (Au⁰). In the second step, growth and stabilization result in the AuNPs formation (Figure 3). Finally, the color change of the resulting solution indicates the formation of AuNPs [Javed, R.; et al. (2020), Mikhailova, E.O. (2021)]. The chemical reactions involved in the reduction of Au³⁺ to Au⁰ in the presence of H₂O molecules are expressed in the below reactions:

A variety of compounds (enzymes, phenols, sugars, etc.) can participate in the reduction and stabilization of different types of particles, including AuNPs [Gu, X. et al. (2021)].

Figure 3. Schematic representation of AuNPs biosynthesis mechanism (Santhosh, P. B. et al. (2022))

5. CHARACTERIZATION OF AuNPs

A variety of characterization approaches are used to verify the effective synthesis of AuNPs and comprehend their characteristics, including:

1. UV-Vis Spectroscopy

AuNP production is UV-Vis spectroscopy depending on the size and shape of the particle, the distinctive surface plasmon resonance (SPR) of AuNPs causes a peak in the UV-Vis spectrum between 520 and 540 nm [Rai et al. (2014) and Rajesh et al. (2015)].

The reduction of aqueous HAuCl₄ ions during reaction with the onion extract was followed by UV-vis spectroscopy. Figure 4 shows the UV-vis absorption spectra recorded from the onion extract, prepared from an aqueous AuNPs solution. A strong resonance at 540 nm is seen and arises due to the excitation of surface plasmon vibrations in the AuNPs [Parida, U. K., Bindhani, B. K., and Nayak, P. (2011)].

Figure 4. UV-vis absorption spectra of gold nanoparticles, (Parida, U. K., et al. (2011))

2. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

The size distribution and shape of the produced nanoparticles are described in depth by TEM. The size, shape, and dispersion of the AuNPs are visible in TEM pictures. When *Allium cepa* is used to create AuNPs, TEM examination usually reveals spherical nanoparticles with a size range of 10 to 50 nm. Depending on the onion extract concentration and reaction parameters, some agglomeration may be seen, however, the majority of the particles are normally well-dispersed [Kumar et al. (2017)].

Narayan et al. (2008) reported the extracellular synthesis of AuNPs using coriander leaf extract as the reducing agent. TEM images have shown the formation of stable AuNPs in the size range of 6.75-57.91 nm Figure 5 with varying shapes, such as spherical, triangle, truncated triangles, and decahedral morphologies.

Figure 5. (A, B) TEM images of AuNPs synthesized by leaf extract of coriander, (Santhosh, P. B. et al. (2022))

3. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM images typically reveal that AuNPs synthesized via green synthesis methods are spherical and well-dispersed. SEM can also detect irregularly shaped particles or aggregates, which may occur depending on the synthesis conditions such as extract concentration and reaction time. In the case of AuNPs synthesized using onion extract, SEM images typically show spherical and occasionally polyhedral particles. The particle sizes range from 10 to 50 nm, and the nanoparticles are generally uniformly distributed without much aggregation. However, variations in the morphology are observed depending on the concentration of the onion extract and the pH of the solution [Sharma et al. (2019)].

4. X-ray diffraction (XRD)

XRD is used to determine the crystallinity and phase of the synthesized nanoparticles. The diffraction peaks correspond to the face-centered cubic (fcc) structure of gold [Mittal et al. (2016)]. Structural characterization has been performed using XRD analysis and the typical XRD pattern for gold nanoparticles is shown in Figure 6. In

In addition to these three peaks, there are some unidentified peaks appeared in the XRD pattern. The characteristic peaks corresponding to (111), (200), and (220) of Au are located at $2\theta = 38.29^\circ$, 44.43° and 64.68° , respectively. The result indicates that the sample is composed of crystalline gold [Parida, U. K., et al. (2011)].

Figure 6. XRD of gold nanoparticle (Parida, U. K., et al. (2011))

5. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR spectroscopy is used to identify the functional groups present in the onion extract that are involved in reducing and stabilizing the AuNPs. It helps to understand the interactions between the phytochemicals and the nanoparticle surface. FTIR spectra show characteristic peaks corresponding to hydroxyl (-OH), carbonyl (C=O), and sulfur-containing groups. These peaks suggest the involvement of flavonoids, phenolic acids, and sulfur compounds from the onion extract in the reduction and stabilization of AuNPs [Shukla et al. (2015) and Sharma et al. (2020)].

6. Zeta Potential Analysis

Zeta potential is used to assess the surface charge of the nanoparticles, which is an indicator of colloidal stability. A high positive or negative zeta potential value implies that the nanoparticles are stable and less likely to aggregate. The zeta potential of AuNPs synthesized using onion is typically negative, indicating the presence of negatively charged bioactive molecules on the nanoparticle surface. Zeta potential values around -20 to -30 mV suggest good stability of the colloidal solution [Singh et al. (2016)].

6. BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES

These biologically synthesized AuNPs have demonstrated significant potential in various biomedical applications, including antioxidant, antibacterial, antifungal, and anticancer activities. This review focuses on the biological activities of AuNPs synthesized from onion and their implications for therapeutic applications.

1. Antioxidant Activity

Oxidative stress is a major contributor to several illnesses, such as cancer, neurological conditions, and cardiovascular diseases. It is brought on by an imbalance between the body's capacity to detoxify reactive intermediates (ROS) and the generation of ROS. To neutralize ROS and shield cells from oxidative damage, antioxidants are essential. Because of the phytochemicals in the onion extract that cling to the surface of the nanoparticles, AuNPs made onion have demonstrated strong antioxidant activity.

AuNPs synthesized using onion extract showed good DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging activity in research by Rai et al. (2014), suggesting their potential as natural antioxidants. According to the study, there may be a dose-dependent antioxidant effect since the nanoparticles' capacity to scavenge grew as their concentration rose. In the development of treatments intended to mitigate disorders associated with oxidative stress, this feature is extremely desirable.

2. Antibacterial Activity

There is an immediate need for novel antimicrobial medicines due to the growth of bacteria that are resistant to antibiotics. Because AuNPs may interact with bacterial cell membranes, cause disruptions to cell functioning, and ultimately cause cell death, they have emerged as a possible option. Potential options for antimicrobial therapy, AuNPs derived from onion extract have shown strong antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. AuNPs synthesized utilizing onion extract showed strong antibacterial action against Gram-negative *Escherichia coli* and Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* in research by Kumar *et al.* (2017). Because Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria have different cell wall compositions, it is possible that the nanoparticles worked better against *E. coli*. This implies that AuNPs derived from onion extract may find application as all-purpose antibacterial agents. The conservation of natural resource reuse of retrieved heavy metal as pesticide formulation in control of disease of ornamentals and vegetables of great market value has emerged as advanced technology as it discourages the fresh heavy metal consumption for synthesis of pesticides available in the market Singh, M. *et al.* (2016), and S Verghese P. (2016).

3. Antifungal Activity

Fungal infections, especially those brought on by harmful fungi like *Candida albicans*, can be extremely dangerous for those with weakened immune systems. Conventional antifungal medications frequently have little effectiveness and can cause resistance to grow. Because onion is used to synthesize AuNPs, these particles have shown antifungal activity and might be used to treat fungal infections. AuNPs made from onion extract showed antifungal efficacy against *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* in research by Singh *et al.* (2016). The research demonstrated these nanoparticles' potential as strong antifungal medicines, especially when used against forms of the disease resistant to traditional antifungal medications. The mixture of potassium palmitate and pyrethroids, pyrethroids and potassium stearate are found to be non-persistent effective on insecticides against whiteflies found on bean plants, Verghese, S., & Jain, D. (2016). This implies that AuNPs produced by synthesizing onion extract may be investigated as substitute therapies for fungal infections.

4. Anticancer Activity

Due to AuNPs' capacity to selectively target cancer cells while causing the least amount of harm to healthy tissues, their anticancer potential has been extensively investigated. Using a variety of cancer cell lines, AuNPs made from *Allium cepa* extract have demonstrated encouraging antitumor potential. AuNPs have special qualities that make them perfect for cancer treatment, including their tiny size, vast surface area, and capacity to be functionalized with targeted molecules.

AuNPs synthesized using onion extract were evaluated against human breast cancer cells (MCF-7) and showed considerable cytotoxicity, according to research by Das *et al.* (2019). The NPS selectively targeted malignant

tissues as evidenced by their ability to cause apoptosis in cancer cells while not affecting healthy cells. This selective cytotoxicity is essential for creating tailored cancer treatments with low adverse effects.

5. Anti-inflammatory Activity

Chronic inflammation is linked to several illnesses, such as cancer, diabetes, and cardiovascular disorders. Inflammation is a complicated biological reaction to infection or injury. Because AuNPs produced from onion extract have demonstrated anti-inflammatory qualities, they may find use in the management of inflammatory conditions. AuNPs made from onion extract decreased inflammation in an animal model of arthritis, according to research by Sharma *et al.* (2020). As evidence of their potential as anti-inflammatory drugs, the nanoparticles decreased edema in the afflicted joints and blocked the production of pro-inflammatory markers.

7. ADVANTAGES OF GREEN SYNTHESIS OF AuNPS

The green synthesis method offers the following advantages over the chemical methods:

1. Safety: this method avoids the exposure of chemicals or their toxic byproducts, either during the NPs synthesis step or during their stabilization process;
2. Cost-effective: no external stabilizing agent is required. On the contrary, chemical methods use expensive and hazardous chemicals and stabilizing agents;
3. Simplicity: biosynthesis of NPs from plant extract is a simple process;
4. Renewable feedstock: e.g., algal biomass;
5. Easy availability of source materials;

6. Biocompatibility: since natural sources are used to synthesize and stabilize the particles, AuNPs synthesized via green synthesis methods are biocompatible with different cell types;
7. The whole green synthesis process is dynamic, reproducible, and energy-efficient;
8. Suitable for large-scale production of NPs for commercial applications;
9. AuNPs synthesized via the green synthesis method are also reported to exhibit antibacterial, antifungal, anticancer, and anti-inflammatory properties, and antioxidant and catalytic activity due to the presence of phytochemicals from the extract [Usman, A.I. *et al.* (2019), Nadeem, M. *et al.* (2017)].

All these factors have rendered the green synthesis approach more rewarding than conventional methods.

1. CHALLENGES AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

In the recent decade, the green synthesis approach has been successfully used to synthesize a variety of NPs, including AuNPs, with varying morphology and properties. Numerous research articles have been published worldwide on the interdisciplinary routes in the synthesis of NPs from different plants and microorganisms. However, there are several limitations and drawbacks in the green synthesis method which limit their largescale production for commercial purposes and diminish their subsequent applications in biotechnology and nanomedicine. The current challenges are summarized below:

1. Insufficient information to regulate NP size and shape: Several investigations have shown that AuNPs with various morphologies can arise throughout the synthesis process. For pharmacological and biological purposes, NPs must develop with a consistent shape and a restricted size distribution. To tackle this issue, attention must be given to optimizing the reaction mixture, experimental duration, pH, temperature, rotating speed, concentrations of chloroauric acid, etc.
2. Absence of standardized procedures to duplicate NPs with identical traits: Even within the same plant, distinct portions might have varied NP structures and characteristics. For example, different plant parts' synthesized AuNPs have varying cytotoxicity levels because of changes in their antioxidant and metabolite contents.
3. One of the main disadvantages is the lack of a well-understood mechanism for NP synthesis. Additionally, it might be difficult to identify essential components found in various metabolites from microbial and plant sources that are actively involved in NP synthesis.
4. Another crucial but unresolved issue is the separation and purification of NPs from the complicated reaction mixture.
5. One of the main concerns is the scalability of synthesized nanoparticles from a laboratory method to satisfy the enormous demands on the industrial and medicinal scale.
6. To expand the use of the biosynthesized NPs in other domains, a thorough toxicological investigation is essential.
7. The scale-up process is hampered by technical obstacles and regulatory rules that prohibit the commercial synthesis of NPs, which must be changed.
8. Stability and functionalization: Additional studies on green synthesis are needed to surface-modify the produced NPs to increase their stability in biological conditions and to functionalize them with certain peptides or antibodies to enhance their use in cancer treatment and medication administration. Notwithstanding the widespread popularity of the green synthesis technique, resolving the aforementioned issues may increase the commercial synthesis of AuNPs' acceptance and adaptability on a worldwide scale. Future work in this field should focus on developing new, standardized procedures, addressing current obstacles, creating safe, intelligent AuNPs functionalized with various biomolecules, and identifying moieties for multifunctional applications [Santhosh, P. B. *et al.* (2022)].

8. CONCLUSION

The conclusion of the review emphasizes the significant advantages of bio-inspired, green synthesis methods for producing AuNPs over traditional chemical methods. Biological agents such as plants, algae, fungi, and biomolecules are used in green synthesis, which provides a biocompatible, economical, and environmentally benign substitute for traditional harmful chemical methods. The manufacturing of AuNPs, which have outstanding qualities including antibacterial, antifungal, anticancer, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory effects, is made safer, more sustainable, and more scalable with the help of these techniques. Given its biological characteristics and efficiency in reducing gold ions to generate stable nanoparticles, onion extract is emphasized as a particularly interesting candidate for application in AuNP production. Large-scale manufacturing is also compatible with the

green synthesis technique, which makes it appropriate for a range of commercial and biological applications. Because of its increased biological activity, ease of use, and environmental friendliness, green synthesis of AuNPs is generally preferable and will be perfect for use in materials science, environmental restoration, and medicine in the future. Conservation of natural resources through sustainable use of plant materials

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